

severely infested fields were essentially zero. The problem was serious throughout the rice bowl region, from the Benue River floodplain through Anambra, Cross River, and northern Imo State—an estimated 50,000 ha of rice.

Most farmers use varietal mixes, but no resistant or escape plants were seen in severely affected fields. Holdings in the area average about 0.5 ha; many farmers harvested no grain.

Although GM has been seen in the

West African savannah for many years, this is the most serious outbreak on record. Situations in 1988 that apparently favored the pest included unusually high rainfall early in the wet season (Jun-Aug); increased rice hectareage stimulated by price increases; small farmholdings with a wide range of planting dates that allowed continuous buildup of the pest population; and ample areas of grassy weeds surrounding the swamps that acted as alternate hosts.

Routine pesticide use is not appropriate for most farmers in this zone because of financial and logistical constraints, and health and environmental hazards. Intensification of breeding for varietal resistance is needed. We will test resistant germplasm from Asia at Abakaliki and Bida (also in the savannah zone) in the 1989 wet season to identify possible donors of resistance. □

Response of rice pests to mercury vapor light and black light traps

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We compared the efficiency of two traps—a Modified Robinson Light Trap (MRL-T) with 80, 125, and 160 W mercury vapor lamps and a Krishi Prakash Black Light Trap (KPBL-T) with 40 W black light tube. The traps were located a minimum isolation distance of 100 m apart. Data were collected for 10 wk (19 Nov 1984-28 Jan 1985).

Catch of insects in different intensities of mercury and black light traps.^a Madurai, India.

Trap	Insects collected (no.)				
	Total	Stem borer	Leaffolder	Brown planthopper	Green leafhopper
MRL-T (125 W)	18,943.2 (3.10) a	3,262.3 (3.24) a	700.0 (2.53) b	12,556.8 (3.26) a	59,253.5 (3.45) a
MRL-T (80 W)	15,770.4 (3.11) a	3,140.3 (3.21) a	642.2 (2.45) b	14,943.8 (3.27) a	44,355.1 (3.51) a
MRL-T (160 W)	11,244.9 (2.92) b	2,233.4 (3.06) a	327.5 (2.11) b	10,021.5 (3.13) a	32,397.2 (3.41) a
KPBL-T (40 W)	1,373.6 (2.83) b	2,287.0 (3.05) a	1,063.5 (1.89) a	839.5 (2.64) b	1,304.3 (2.73) b

^aMean of 10 wk. Figures in parentheses are transformed values. In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

MRL-T 125 W collected 40% and MRL-T 80 W 33% of all insects collected (see table). Stem borers were more attracted to

MRL-T 125 W; leaffolders to the KPBL-T. Brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers were more attracted to the MRL-T. □

Sex and reproductive status of rice stem borers and leaffolders attracted to black light trap

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We examined the sex ratio and reproductive status of rice yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.) and rice leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) attracted to a 20 W black light trap. Insects were collected for 10 d the first 14 d of Nov 1984, when activity peaked. More YSB females than males were

Reproductive status of SB and LF attracted to black light trap.

Days	Stem borer					Leaffolder				
	Total	Male	Female	Gravid females	Spent females	Total	Male	Female	Gravid females	Spent females
1	118	10	108	55	53	323	156	167	93	74
2	174	18	156	92	64	334	143	191	118	73
3	195	12	183	105	78	328	164	164	96	68
4	258	14	244	140	104	232	104	128	78	50
5	306	16	290	160	130	328	135	193	120	73
6	197	9	188	126	62	224	98	126	86	40
7	98	4	94	63	31	158	84	74	44	30
8	340	6	334	186	148	214	115	99	58	41
9	188	12	176	113	63	69	34	35	23	12
10	360	15	345	200	145	112	55	57	35	22
Total ^a	2234	116 (5.2)	2118 (94.8)	1240 (58.6)	878 (41.6)	2322	1088 (46.9)	1234 (53.1)	751 (60.9)	483 (39.1)

^aValues in parentheses are percentage of the total and of females, respectively.

attracted (see table); the male-to-female ratio was as high as 1:18. There were more gravid females (58.6%) than spent ones (41.6%).

The ratio of male to female LF attracted was more or less equal. Of the total females, 61% were gravid and 39% spent. □